

The use of organic binders in monumental *terracruda* sculpture: integrating Sanskrit texts with spectroscopic and spectrometric data in the study of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut examples (Kabul, Afghanistan, 5th to 11th centuries CE)

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Abstract

This work is part of a broader research project aimed at understanding the technology of making monumental *terracruda* (air-dried clay) sculptures and contributing to the design of specific recovery protocols and conservation treatments for archaeological examples. Previous studies have been mainly based on information recovered by petrographic, mineralogical, chemical and botanical characterization performed on Afghan examples from Buddhist sites of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut (5th to 11th centuries) and the study of related traditional knowledge preserved in India.

Here the focus is to verify the hypothesis of the addition of possible organic binding substances to elaborate the modelling pastes. So far, the studies that have looked for them have done so with the aim of analysing painting techniques. However, ancient sacred texts (8th-17th centuries CE) mention a wide use of organic substances also in the preparation of clays. In a pioneering approach aimed at elucidating their presence in the modelling pastes, we used a staggered analytical approach as part of a European

IPERION-HS project (FIX 134) with first, FTIR analyses to verify the presence of organic binders and if possible their specific groups and secondly, GC-MS analyses to characterize more accurately the organic binders in presence. Finally, we used a structural analytical approach based on MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry to study the polysaccharides and access their taxonomic information. This method, based on a partial polysaccharide digestion using specific enzymes to overcome the limitations of monosaccharide-based analysis achieved using GC-MS, was adapted to the study of monumental *terracruda* sculptural fragments from the Buddhist sites of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut. The results suggest that multiple organic binders were added, consistent with the complex processes described in ancient sacred literature related to the preparation of clays and plasters.

1. Introduction and research aim

Monumental *terracruda* sculptures are large-sized sculptures connected to an architecture or environment whose main material for their making is unfired or air-dried clay (*terracruda* as opposed to *terracotta*, as clay sculptures are usually named when fired). They need a core (made of wood, stone or bricks) as a base to add different modelling layers, prepared differently depending on whether they are internal (more clayey and with more straw and fibres), external (sandier and with less fibrous admixtures) or finishing layers (often referred to as stucco because of its usually white appearance), to achieve the desired size, shape and aspect, ranging from the smallest than human-sized to large or colossal figures (López-Prat et al. 2024).

The first examples following this elaboration method that allows modelling big-size sculptures employing *terracruda* as the main material for their making appeared in Central Asia – Afghanistan region around the 2nd century BC, before the arrival of Buddhism to the region. However, this kind of sculpture started to become common inside Buddhism, in a great manner after the 3rd century CE, spreading from Central Asia and the northwest of the Indian subcontinent (present-day Pakistan and Afghanistan) to China and the Himalayas (Ladakh, Tibet, Bhutan), being Japan the country where historical-archaeological examples are documented located further east (López-Prat et al. 2024).

A broader and interdisciplinary project was built to understand the technique behind this kind of sculpture. Until now, we focused on archaeometrically studying the examples of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut through MC-tomography (López-Prat et al. 2021), botanical (López-Prat et al. 2022), petrographic, mineralogical and chemical, analyses (López-Prat et al. 2023), comparing the results with data provided by the documentation of Indian traditional knowledge. Today, Bengali artists, the *kumors*, masters of the sacred art of modelling divinity out of raw earth and connoisseurs of sacred literature concerning the subject, only add organic binding substances in the priming layers that prepare the sculpture to receive colour, usually binding chalk or kaolinite with a mixture of a secret tamarind gum-based compound (López-Prat et al. 2021). Nevertheless, sacred texts ranging from the 8th to the 17th centuries and

belonging to Agama literature mention the addition of multiple organic binders also in the clays-based pastes necessary for the creation of an air-dried clay sculpture (Varma 1970). Due to the complexity of what is detailed in them (the high number of admixtures needed and the steps that must be followed to obtain the modelling pastes needed to make a sculpture), these recipes have been viewed as having a ritual or symbolic value (Luczanits 2004:15). When scientific analyses have focused in evidencing the use of organic binders in monumental *terracruda* sculpture have done so in a subordinate way in the study of polychromies (Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2017, Bonaduce *et al.* 2019, Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2022, Taniguchi *et al.* 2022).

In this paper, we explore the hypothesis of the presence of organic compounds in the mortars of eleven fragments of architectural decoration (including sculpture, reliefs and mural paintings) coming from the Afghan Buddhist sites of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut (5th-11th century CE). To verify their presence, FTIR, GC-MS and MALDI-TOF MS analyses were carried out thanks to the access to the European IPERION HS infrastructure (project 'STICK: SculpTure In terraCruda: advancing its Knowledge'). Special attention was given to the identification of gums, starting from the hypothesis of their probable presence in sculpture both because of their use today in West Bengal (India), as well as their mention in the Agama literature (Varma 1970) and the scientific evidence of having been found in the pastes of other monumental Afghan *terracruda* sculptures during the study of polychromies and painting techniques (Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2017, Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2022, Taniguchi *et al.* 2022).

2. The Agama literature

The technology of representing the sacred using air-dried clay (*terracruda*) as the main material is explained in detail in Agama literature, a collection of scriptures belonging to the Shakta, Shaiva, and Vaishnava devotional schools. These texts were the basis for K.M. Varma's capital work "The Indian Technique of Clay Modelling" (1970). In it, Varma mentions the *Kashyapasilpa* (ca. 12th century CE) as the main source for the study of the technique "supplemented by the valuable points that can be drawn from the other texts," that is, the *Vimanarchanakalpa* (ca. 8th century CE), the *Kashyapajnankanda* (ca. 16th century CE), and the *Samurtarchanadhikarana* (ca. 16th–17th centuries CE). These texts explain in detail the process of making a sacred image out of air dried clay using seven materials, which are paralleled by the 'elements' that make up a human body: the wooden armature (*sula*) is the skeleton; the ropes (*raju*) are the veins and sinew; the different layers of clay (*mrt*) are the flesh; the clothes (*pata*) in the final layers of clay are the skin; the glue (*astabandha*), is the fat; the "limestone paste" (*sarkarakalka*) is the blood; and the colour (*varna*) is the life force (Varma 1970).

In particular, according to Agama literature, among the seven "elements" that make up the construction of an air-dried clay sculpture, three are particularly interesting here, as they mention using organic binders. These are, in order of preparation:

a) The glue (*astabandha*), which according to Varma means "the binding medium or glue prepared from eight materials". Composed of different plant resins, molasses, turpentine, red chalk or red ochre, ghee, and sesame oil (Varma 1970: 11-12).

b) The clay (*mrt*), "selected from rivers, ponds and lakes must be well cleaned (...) It is obtained from three types of soil: *jangala* (sandy soil); *anupa* (moist soil); *misra* (mixed soil) (...) The mud or slime (*panka*) should be obtained from these three soil types. It must be prepared separately with the same process" consisting of 12 steps during which, in short, the soils are first stirred, filtered and decanted and then, at different stages, numerous admixtures of various origins (plant, animal and mineral) are added. Among those of plant origin, there are decoctions of the bark of trees, such as different species of *Ficus*; decoctions of fruits as the three *Myrobalans*; flours, such as barley and wheat flours; resins, such as that of the *Pinus Longifolia* and *Amyris Agallochum*; gums as dried secretions of *Feronia Elephantum* (*kapittha*) and *Aegle Marmelos* (*bilva*); sesame oil (*taila*) and spices such as pepper (*marici*), saffron (*kunkuma*) and sandal powder (*candana*). Among admixtures of mineral origin, "crushed stone," "sea sand" and "river sand" are mentioned, as well as some varieties of "dust" in the eleventh stage of clays preparation: "earth sought from the house of a crab" (*kuliravasa*), "the hill of white ants" (*valmika*) or "earth from the beginning of the stalks of the rice plant" (*sasyamula*). Finally, among the admixtures of animal origin, the following ingredients are included: milk, yoghurt, clarified butter and honey. In the last stage, the twelfth, coconut husk fibres must be cut and added to the clay in a ratio of 1:4 (Varma 1970: 19-23).

c) The “*sarkarakalka*” (a word which, according to Varma, offers some doubts when it comes to translating it, opting to translate it as ‘limestone paste’). To prepare it “after the selection of *sarkaras* (limestones), one should wash it and get them dried. When they have dried out completely, a very fine powder should be made. This powder should be ground very well on a grinding-stone, adding the decoction made from Myrobalans, viz. fruits of *Terminalia Chebula*, *Terminalia Bellerica* and *Philantus Emblica*. Out of this paste, one should make balls which should be allowed to dry completely”. The *sarkarakalka* is employed in various layers and prepared differently for each layer adding the dried secretion of the tree *Feronia Elephantum* (*kapitha*) diluted in water in different proportions depending on the suited consistence for each layer. It is mentioned that a certain amount of cotton must also be added to the mixture (Varma 1970: 26-27).

3. The Buddhist sites of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut (5th to 11th centuries of the CE)

Our analytical approach to study the use of organic binders in producing sculpture plasters has been performed on fragments from the sculptural repertoire of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut. These are two Buddhist sites, separated by ca. 400 m., lying on the eastern slopes of the Hindukush Mountain chain, only a few kilometres to the south of the present-day city of Kabul (Afghanistan), overlooking the natural lake of Qol-e-Hashmat Khan.

Tepe Narenj was the location of a Buddhist monastery that was active between the 5th and 10th centuries CE. Between 2004 and 2011, the archaeological excavations uncovered an architectural complex system of terraces with three levels (lower, middle, and upper) interconnected by a system of steps and platforms (Paiman, 2012). On the terraces in the middle portion of the site stood a series of cult chapels with the remains of multiple examples of monumental *terracruda* sculptures preserved. The ensembles documented at Tepe Narenj consisted of life-size or colossal figures placed inside chapels and linked to iconographic programs of Buddhist cosmology, some identified with the Tantric tradition (Paiman 2010).

Qol-e-Tut was also a monastic complex active between the sixth and the 11th centuries CE (Paiman, 2018). Archaeological excavations between 2008 and 2013 also revealed a complex network of buildings arranged on terraces, where several chapels, two stupas, and various monastic cells were erected. The architectural remains presented mural paintings and important sculptural findings. The presence of sculptures at Qol-e-tut was essentially represented by large feet preserved *in situ* on pedestals, highlighting a colossal polychromed Buddha in its original position erected in Chapel 13, two small figures in Chapel 15, and many sculptural fragments recovered during the excavation and preserved in the various rooms of the monastic complex.

Tepe-Narenj and Qol-e-tut are two of the best surviving examples of Afghan Buddhist archaeology, especially because of the importance of the preserved *in situ* monumental *terracruda* sculptural decoration linked to Gandharan art (Figure 1).

Figure 1. (a) Location of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut. (b) Example of the half body of a monumental *terracruda* sculpture preserved in Chapel 3 at Tepe Narenj. (c) Remains (left foot) of a standing Buddha in Chapel 7 (Qol-e-tut). (d) Map of Tepe Narenj highlighting the chapels and the original location (highlighted with orange dots) of the studied samples TN1 to TN7. (e) Map of Qol-e-tut highlighting the original location of the studied samples. The orange dot corresponds to the original location of the samples QT1, QT2, and QT3 (Chapel 13), and the red dot to the sample QT4 (Chapel 6). Maps courtesy of Z. Paiman.

4. Materials and methods

4.1 The samples

Sampling was conducted in July 2018, thanks to an agreement with the Archaeological Institute of Afghanistan (AIA) that allowed samples to be exported to Europe with all the necessary permissions. Sampling was based on the premise of not damaging the remains still *in situ* and according to a criterion of morphological representativeness based on the findings preserved in the different chapels of the two monastic complexes of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut. In addition to *terracruda* sculpture, fragments from mural surfaces (with and without decoration) were collected to observe potential technical differences between the various architectural elements. A total of eleven samples have been studied, coming from the two sites (Table 1):

1. Seven fragments of sculptures preserving one or several layers. From Tepe Narenj: TN1 and TN2 (taken from Chapel 1), TN3 (from Chapel 3), TN5 (from Chapel 4) and TN7 (from Chapel 5). From Qol-e-tut: QT2 (from Chapel 13) and QT4 (from Chapel 6) (Figure 2).
2. Two fragments of mural paintings or reliefs: TN4 (from Chapel 4 of Tepe Narenj) and QT1 (from Chapel 13 of Qol-e-tut) (Supplementary Information 1).
3. Two samples from the walls surface of the most representative rooms preserving sculptural decoration in situ (TN6 from Chapel 4 of Tepe Narenj and QT3 taken from Chapel 13 of Qol-e-tut) (Supplementary Information 2).

As said above, except TN6 and QT3, extracted directly from the wall surface, the sampled fragments were preserved close to their respective sculptural or mural origin.

Table 1. List of the analysed samples, with subsamples ID and description.

SCULPTURE			
Sample ID	Location	Subsample ID	Description
TN1 (Clothing fragment)	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 1 (recovered from a basket deposited on the central pedestal)	TN1 a	Primer layer (Munsell 10YR 7/3)
		TN1 b	Light brown clay-based layer (Munsell 0YR 6/3)
TN2 (Possible fragment of halo with incised decoration)	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 1 (recovered from a basket deposited above the stone socle of the south wall)	TN2 a	"Barbottina" layer (Munsell 10R 5/6)
		TN2 b	Reddish clay-based layer (Munsell 2.5YR 5/6)
		TN2 c	Brown clay-based layer (Munsell 10YR 7/3)
TN3 (Possible internal body fragment)	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 3 (placed above the legs of sculpture four - north)	TN3	Brown clay-based layer (Munsell 7.5YR 6/4)
TN5 (Hair fragment)	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 4 (recovered from a basket near the entrance door)	TN5	White stucco layer with incised curved lines
TN7 (Finger fragment)	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 5 (recovered from a basket placed on the top of the pedestal attached to the northern wall)	TN7a	White stucco layer
		TN7b	Brown clay-based layer (Munsell 10YR 6/3)
QT2 (Clothing fragment)	Qol-e-tut - Chapel 13 (recovered from a basket placed at the foot of the "Colossal Buddha")	QT2_a	Pigmented layer (Munsell 2.5YR 7/6)
		QT2_b	White stucco layer
		QT2_c	Brown clay-based layer (Munsell 10YR 7/3)
QT4 (fragment of a toe)	Qol-e-tut - Chapel 6 (recovered from foot fragments preserved next to the remains of the right foot of a monumental Buddha)	QT4	Brown clay-based layer (Munsell 7.5 YR 5/4)
RELIEF AND MURAL PAINTING			
Sample ID	Location	Subsample ID	Description
TN4 (Relief fragment)	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 4 (recovered from a basket near the entrance door)	TN4	Brown clay-based mortar (Munsell 10YR 6/3) with a red polychromed surface finish
QT1 (Mural painting fragment)	Qol-e-tut - Chapel 13 (recovered from a basket placed at the foot of the "Colossal Buddha")	QT1	Brown clay-based mortar (Munsell 10YR 6/3) with blue and red polychromed surface finish

WALLS			
Sample ID	Location	Subsample ID	Description
TN6	Tepe Narenj - Chapel 4 (north wall, originally in contact with the back of a sculpture)	TN6	Brown clay-based mortar (Munsell 10YR 6/3)
QT3	Chapel 13 Qol-e-tut (northern wall)	QT3	Brown clay-based mortar (Munsell 10YR 6/3)

Figure 2. Fragments of sculpture sampled.

Based on the hypothesis of the presence of gums, both by the study of traditional knowledge in West Bengal (India) for preparing some of the finishing layers (López-Prat *et al.* 2021) and their evidence in other Afghan monumental *terracruda* sculptures some samples of reference gums that could be found in antiquity in the Afghan region were also analysed for polysaccharide characterization. In particular, four distinct model gums were analysed. Three commercial gums were distributed in powder: tragacanth and locust bean gums (Sigma Aldrich), and Arabic gum (Kremer Pigmente). Apricot gum was directly extracted from an apricot tree and reduced to power using a mortar. The gums were selected based on the likelihood of having been found in Afghanistan/Central Asia in antiquity or because of their mention in other research on Afghan sculpture, as would be the case of tragacanth gum, detected in the Buddhas of Bamiyan (Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2017) and Tepe Sardar (Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2022). Apricot gum was selected because it was mentioned in the archaeological reports of Barthoux (1930) as being in common use in Afghanistan in the first quarter of the 20th century and because

Prunoideae gums were evidenced as a binding medium for ground layers in Central Asian paintings (Birstein 1975; Lapierre 1990).

4.2. Methods

Samples were sub-sampled in the lab with a scalpel following the presence of different layers when present. All samples were analysed separately for chemical composition by FTIR and GC-MS. Based on the FTIR results and/or previous Epifluorescence analysis (López-Prat et al. 2023) samples TN1a, TN1b, TN2b, TN2c and TN6 were studied using an OMICS approach based on MALDI-TOF analysis specifically developed to identify polysaccharides in cultural heritage samples (Granzotto et al. 2017 & 2024); here the method was adapted to the study of archaeological *terracruda* sculptures.

4.2.1 FTIR

FTIR spectroscopic analysis in transmission mode was performed on all raw samples to verify the presence of organic binders and, if possible, their specific groups (lipids, proteins and/or polysaccharides). To identify individual components by FTIR spectroscopy, a mixture separation by solvent (hexane, ethyl acetate, benzene, chloroform and hot water) extractions was performed on all samples.

FTIR spectroscopy in a transmission mode was performed using a Hyperion 3000 FT-IR microscope coupled with a Tensor spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Inc.) with a liquid nitrogen-cooled MCT detector. The microscope, equipped with a 15x objective suitable for transmission mode measurements, acquired infrared spectra in the 4000 - 600 cm^{-1} range, with 64 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . During measurements and analyses, the system was operated using the proprietary 32-bit software OPUS 8.1 (Bruker Optik GmbH).

All FTIR spectra were processed using OPUS software, provided by Bruker. FTIR analyses were conducted at the Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia.

4.2.2 GC-MS

In a second phase, GC-MS analyses were performed in all samples at the Heritage Science Lab of Ljubljana (University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology).

The samples were grinded (approximately 1 mg) and treated according to the method published by Retko et al. (2020). Samples were concentrated 20x and transferred to vials with 250 μL glass inserts. Each sample was analysed in 3 parallels (Retko et al. 2020), with the exception of samples QT2a in two parallels and TN2a in one parallel

due to the size of the sample. Thermo Scientific Focus GC coupled with ISQ MS was used to identify the fatty acid esters, which were separated on the Supelco OmegawaxTM 320 capillary column with a diameter of 320 μm , a length of 30 m and a stationary phase (bound polyethylene glycol phase) thickness of 0.25 μm .

Due to the uniqueness of the TN2 and the results obtained in its study by FTIR, GC-MS and MALDI-TOF MS analysis, TN2b and TN2c were also analyzed by direct methanolic extraction (hereafter acid extraction) (Correa-Ascencio & Evershed 2014) at the University of Barcelona. The extracts were derivatized with N,O-bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (BSTFA) and analysed with a chromatographer Thermo Scientific TS GC ultra, with a silica capillary column of 30 m, 0.25 μm thickness and a mass spectrometer Thermo Scientific ITQ 900 operated in electronic ionization (70 eV). The mass range was m/z 40-650.

In all cases, obtained mass spectra were compared with the NIST library and individual peaks were identified, based on the matching of m/z values of typical fragments.

4.2.3 Polysaccharide characterization

Sculpture samples displaying evidence of organic binders by previous epifluorescence analysis (Lopez-Prat *et al.* 2023), i.e. in TN1a, TN1b, TN2b and TN2c, and of polysaccharides by FTIR analysis, i.e. in TN2b and TN6, were studied using an integrated analytical approach to identify plant gums using their saccharide fingerprints obtained by MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry analysis. The protocol based on a controlled enzymatic hydrolysis was adapted from a previous work (Granzotto *et al.* 2017) and it was applied to model gums (Arabic, locust bean, tragacanth and apricot gums) and archaeological samples. Briefly, starting from 100 mg of archaeological sample, polysaccharides were solubilized in water and cleaved either by exo- β -1,3-galactanase from *Clostridium thermocellum* in ammonium phosphate 50 mM, pH 6 at 50 °C or endo-1,4- β -mannanase from *Cellvibrio japonicus* in ammonium phosphate 50 mM, pH 7.5 at 37 °C. Exo- β -1,3-galactanase specifically ensures the *endo*-hydrolysis of (1,4)- β -D-galactose linkages in (1,4)- β -galactans and type I arabinogalactans. Endo-1,4- β -mannanase randomly hydrolyses (1,4)-Beta-D-mannosidic linkages in mannans, galactomannans and glucomannans. Mass spectrometry analyses were performed using an Ultraflex III MALDI-ToFTof (Bruker Daltonics) in positive mode. Both 3-AQ (3-aminoquinoline, derivatizing agent) and DHB/DMA (2,5-Dihydroxybenzoic acid in N,N-dimethylaniline) matrices were evaluated to provide the best quality spectra. Reflectron mode was chosen to reach the highest mass accuracy over the desired m/z range (from 700 to 4500). Data were treated manually using the flexAnalysis software (Bruker Daltonics).

5. Results

5.1 FTIR results

After extraction with different organic solvents FTIR analyses displayed bands evidencing natural organic compounds in samples QT2c, TN1b, TN2b, TN2c and TN6. Transmission FTIR spectra of samples TN2b, TN2c, TN6 and QT2c are illustrated in Figure XY. Bands corresponding to proteins (~ 1650 , ~ 1542 cm^{-1}) were observed in samples QT2c, TN2b, TN2c and TN6; and lipids (~ 2924 , ~ 2853 and ~ 1740 cm^{-1}) in TN2b and TN6. Two strong FTIR signals of aromatic C=C stretching vibrations, located at ~ 1600 and ~ 1515 cm^{-1} , suggest the presence of phenolic lignans such as pinosresinol in samples TN2b and TN6 (see Figure 3_A, C) (Ivić *et al.* 2022). Other absorbance bands (1436, 1266, 1203, 1168, 834 cm^{-1}) along with these two signals could indicate the presence of Pinaceae pine resins (Coppola *et al.* 2023). Bands corresponding to natural polysaccharides (2924, 1607, 1436, 1379, 1240, 1113, 1072 and 1054 cm^{-1}) seem present in both samples (Thombare *et al.* 2023). Additionally, carboxylates were found in TN2b, and oxalates (~ 1630 , ~ 1320 cm^{-1}) in TN2a and TN2c (Figure 3). Furthermore, the FTIR band of carbonyl (C=O) stretching vibration placed at 1731 cm^{-1} , common in many organic compounds, was found in TN1a and TN7b.

Figure 3. Transmission FTIR spectra collected on samples A) TN2_b, B) TN2_c, C) TN6 and D) QT2_c.

Besides clay, various inorganic components such as calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium carbonate (calcite) and calcium magnesium carbonate (dolomite) were also identified. In samples TN1 and TN3, bands corresponding to Paraloid B-72 were identified (2984, 2952, 1730, 1448, 1387, 1237, 1147, and 1026 cm^{-1}), suggesting contamination by restoration materials used during

archaeological interventions (Paiman 2010). Table 5 provides brief information about identified materials in all investigated samples (QT and TN) by FTIR spectroscopy.

Table 2: Material identification of analysed samples (Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut) by FTIR spectroscopy

Label of sample	Layer	Identified materials by FTIR spectroscopy
TN1	TN1a	calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), silicon dioxide (quartz), extra band: 1731 cm ⁻¹
	TN1b	clay, silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium carbonate (calcite), calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), Paraloid B72
TN2	TN2a	calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), silicon dioxide (quartz), clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), oxalates
	TN2b	clay, silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium carbonate (calcite), Pinaceae pine resins, polysaccharides, lipids, carboxylates
	TN2c	silicon dioxide (quartz), clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), oxalates, proteins
TN3	TN3	clay, calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium carbonate (calcite), cellulose, Paraloid B72
TN4	TN4a	clay, silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium carbonate (calcite)
	TN4b	clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz), cellulose (fibre)
TN5	TN5	calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), calcium magnesium carbonate (dolomite), silicon dioxide (quartz)
TN6	TN6	clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz), lipids, polysaccharides, proteins, Pinaceae pine resins
TN7	TN7_a	calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum)
	TN7_b	clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), extra band: 1731 cm ⁻¹

QT1	QT1	clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz)
QT2	QT2_a	calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum), traces of silicone dioxide (quartz)
	QT2_b	calcium sulphate dihydrate (gypsum)
	QT2_c	clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz), proteins
QT3	QT3	calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz), calcium magnesium carbonate (dolomite), clay
QT4	QT4	clay, calcium carbonate (calcite), silicon dioxide (quartz)

5.2 GC-MS results

In the solutions of the treated samples TN2a, TN2b, TN7b, QT1, QT2a, QT2b, methyl esters of fatty acids were observed in decreasing concentration: palmitic (C_{16:0}), palmitoleic (C_{16:1}), stearic (C_{18:0}), oleic (C_{18:1}) and erucic acids (C_{22:1}), being erucic sometimes higher in concentration than palmitoleic (C_{16:1}), stearic (C_{18:0}) and oleic (C_{18:1}) (Supplementary Information 3).

TN1a, TN1b, TN2b, TN3, TN5, TN7a, TN7b, QT2a, QT2_c, QT3 and QT4 also displayed methyl esters of myristic acid (C_{14:0}), and TN1a, TN2b, TN4, TN5, TN7a, TN7b and QT4 propionic acid.

Table 3. List of the main fatty acids in the samples determined with GC-MS analysis

Label of sample	Main FAs in order of decreasing concentration
TN1a	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > propionic > erucic (C _{22:1})
TN1b	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1})
TN2 a	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1})
TN2 b	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > propionic > oleic (C _{18:1}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1})
TN2c	erucic (C _{22:1}) > palmitic (C _{16:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1})
TN3	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > erucic (C _{22:1})

TN4	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > propionic > erucic (C _{22:1}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1})
TN5	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > propionic
TN6	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > oleic (C _{18:1})
TN7a	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > propionic > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > erucic (C _{22:1})
TN7b	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > propionic
QT1	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1})
QT2a	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1})
QT2b	erucic (C _{22:1}) > palmitic (C _{16:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1})
QT2c	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1})
QT3	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1})
QT4	palmitic (C _{16:0}) > erucic (C _{22:1}) > stearic (C _{18:0}) > myristic (C _{14:0}) > oleic (C _{18:1}) > palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) > propionic

TN2b and TN2c were also analysed at the University of Barcelona following Correa-Ascencio & Evershed (2014) extraction method (Supplementary Information 4). Both samples displayed the presence of palmitic (C_{16:0}), palmitoleic (C_{16:1}), and oleic (C_{18:1}) acids, followed by stearic acid (C_{18:0}). These data suggest a general plant origin of the residues. However, β -sitosterol, was not identified. Cholesterol was identified in both samples and likely derives from contamination (Hammann *et al.* 2018), although it could also come from the presence of animal products. Dehydroabietic acid was present in traces in both samples, indicating the use of Pinaceae products, likely resin. Mid and long-chain *n*-alcohols were identified in both samples (Table 7).

Table 4. List of the main compounds for each sample. In the table: FA=fatty acid.

Label of sample	Main FAs in order of decreasing concentration	Cholesterol	<i>n</i> -alcohols
TN2 b	palmitic (C _{16:0}) palmitoleic (C _{16:1}) oleic (C _{18:1}) myristic (C _{14:0}) stearic (C _{18:0})	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
TN2 c	palmitic (C _{16:0}) palmitoleic (C _{16:1}), oleic (C _{18:1}) myristic (C _{14:0}) stearic (C _{18:0})	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.3 Polysaccharide characterization results

A multi-enzyme protocol based on the use of mannanase and galactanase (Granzotto et al. 2017 & 2024) was used to characterize the polysaccharides. The saccharidic fingerprints were measured using MALDI-TOF analyses with both 3-AQ matrix and DHB. The MALDI-TOF patterns of apricot, Arabic, tragacanth and locust bean gums were used as reference patterns based on the hypothesis of their presence. The analyses proved the presence of polysaccharides in the five archaeological samples analysed. The Figure 4A shows a typical fingerprint of hexose homopolymers identified in TN2c sample. In particular, here are shown polysaccharidic structures ranging from Hex₇ to Hex₁₀, also identified in locust bean gum fingerprint (Figure 4B, Supplementary Information 5). Arabic and apricot gums are displaying different patterns with respectively heteropolysaccharides (Figure 4C, Supplementary Information 5), i.e. Pent₂Hex₃dHex₂ and Pent₂Hex₃dHexHexA also identified in previous works (Granzotto et al. 2017), and homopolysaccharides exhibiting hexose and pentose patterns (Figure 4D) (homopolysaccharidic structures not attributed). Tragacanth is also exhibiting a different pattern from TN2c sample based on homopolysaccharides (Figure 4E) and heteropolysaccharides in the m/z range below 1300 (see Granzotto et al. 2017 in Supplementary Data). One should note a second homopolysaccharidic pattern based on hexose residues (structure not attributed) in the TN2C sample (labelled with an asterisk in the Figure 4A). The Figure 5A is showing this pattern on a broader m/z range ranging from 800-2350. This homopolysaccharidic structure was also identified in the other archaeological samples, namely TN1a, TN1b, TN2b and TN6, but with a poorer signal to noise. Figure 5B to 5E shows the identified markers labelled with the asterisks (m/z 835.130, 997.157, 1158.22 labelled with red, purple and burgundy asterisks respectively). These data are demonstrating the presence of gums in the studied archaeological samples with first structural information. Considering their taxonomy, the polysaccharidic structures identified allow to exclude Arabic, apricot and tragacanth gums from consideration. To further characterize the origin of the gums used by the artists a wider variety of model gums would have to be analysed.

Figure 4. MALDI-TOF MS spectra of enzymatically digested (A) TN2c extract and (B) locust bean gum, (C) Arabic gum, (D) apricot gum and (E) tragacanth gum with the related oligosaccharide attributions. The reported ions correspond to oligosaccharides derivatized with 3-aminoquinoline. The monosaccharide order for each oligosaccharide is arbitrary and does not refer to its structure. (A) and (B) exhibit oligosaccharidic patterns with H^+ , Na^+ and K^+ ions. Blue and green asterisks in D show homopolysaccharidic patterns based on hexose residues and hash symbol shows homopolysaccharidic patterns based on pentose residues. The y axis of the spectrum is the relative intensity.

Figure 5. MALDI-TOF MS spectra of (A) TN2c sample and (B) to (E) respectively TN1a, TN1b, TN2b and TN6 samples - the reported ions correspond to oligosaccharides without 3-aminoquinoline derivatization. Asterisks are showing the homopolysaccharidic patterns based on hexose residues; red, purple and burgundy colours are used to facilitate correlation between spectra.

6. Discussion

Despite the complexity of the results, the preliminary information obtained aimed at evidencing the addition of organic binder compounds in clay-based mortars in the architectural decoration of TN and QT indicates their presence.

A first screening by FTIR highlighted the addition of organic material only in sculpture fragments (TN1, TN2, TN7, and QT2) and in the wall sample originally in contact with the backside of a sculpture (TN6). Bands corresponding to proteins were present in

QT2_c sample (internal clay layer of a fragment of drapery), TN2b (external clay layer of a halo fragment), TN2c (internal clay layer of a halo fragment), and TN6 (sample coming from a surface of a wall initially in contact with the backside of a sculpture); and bands corresponding to the presence of lipids were identified in TN2b and TN6. Natural resins and polysaccharides were detected in samples TN2_b and TN6. Additionally, an unidentified organic component may be present in samples TN1a and TN7b, as indicated by a characteristic signal of carbonyl (C=O) stretching vibration placed at 1731 cm^{-1} in the corresponding FTIR spectra.

The detection through FTIR of organic compounds only in sculpture samples (or in contact with them as TN6) could suggest a more complex mixture of organic substances in modelling plasters of sculptural decoration than in other mural elements (reliefs and paintings). In fact, besides QT2 (a fragment of drapery coming from the colossal Buddha of Chapel 13 of Qol-e-tut), any of the analysed subsamples coming from samples with polychromies (i.e. samples TN4 and QT1, relief and wall painting, respectively) gave any organic band. Neither the polychrome layer of the fragment of drapery (QT2a). Oxalates (in TN2a and TN2c) and carboxylates (in TN2b) were also identified by FTIR spectroscopy; these deterioration compounds were, in our case, most likely formed through chemical reactions between the minerals in the clay and organic acids present in the environment. These acids can come from various sources, including biological activity (e.g., lichens, fungi), pollution, or the breakdown of organic materials. When these acids interact with the minerals in the clay, they form oxalate and carboxylate salts, which then accumulate on the sculpture plasters (Rampazzi 2019). TN2 fragment is also particularly interesting for belonging to a kind of Afghan monumental *terracruda* sculpture finished in a hard red air-dried clay characteristic of the 7th and 8th centuries CE (Forgione 2019), and because it is the only sculpture fragment where homopolysaccharidic structures based on hexose residues (also found in the locust bean gum fingerprint) have been evidenced by the OMICS protocol in its internal clay layer (TN2c). These analyses also evidenced sugars in TN1a, TN1b, TN2b and TN6, a sample taken from the surface of the northern wall of Chapel 4, originally in contact with the backside or internal part of a sculpture. The identification of sugars in the sample analyses suggests that gums were commonly used in the modelling pastes of Afghan monumental *terracruda* sculptures. This is reinforced by the fact that gums were also identified in the study of polychromies of the Giant Buddhas of Bamiyan (Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2017). These investigations outlined the presence of saccharide material (in this case, tragacanth gum from the genus *Astragalus*) in the clay modelling, while milk was found in the plaster layers on top. Tragacanth gum was also found in a clay sculpture sample from Tepe Sardar, Afghanistan (Lliveras-Tenorio *et al.* 2022). It is worth mentioning that Agama literature highlights the addition of *Feronia elephantum* (*Limonia acidissima*) gum in the final steps to prepare the pastes for modelling an air-dried clay sculpture (Varma 1970: 21-22). This gum is also the main binder used to prepare the *sarkarakalka*, the preparation that finishes the sculpture and prepares it for polychromies (Varma 1970: 27-28). In West Bengal - India a tamarind gum-based preparation is used for making the primer layers before polychromies (López-Prat *et al.* 2021).

Besides FTIR analyses, GC-MS analyses performed by the Heritage Science Lab of Ljubljana to study the presence of fatty acids in samples of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut detected palmitic, palmitoleic, myristic, stearic, oleic and erucic acids as a common chromatogram profile. The characteristic presence of erucic acid could suggest the presence of an oil from the family of *Brassicaceae*, which includes mustard oil and rapeseed oil. Mustard plants, particularly *Brassica juncea*, are native to the Indian subcontinent and have been cultivated in South Asia for millennia. Mustard oil is categorized as a semi-drying oil, which means that it has some capacity to harden upon exposure to air but not as effectively as oils with higher polyunsaturated fatty acid content. In particular, it has been traditionally used in earthen construction in the Indian Himalayas for its properties in improving water resistance and the durability of earthen materials (Feiglstorfer 2014). It seems worth mentioning that sesame oil (not compatible with the results of the chromatograms of the Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut sculpture samples) is also a semi-dry oil noted in the Agama literature as an additive for preparing the clay-based pastes required for the manufacture of sacred sculptures (Varma 1970). Moreover, the GC-MS results revealed an unusually high content of palmitoleic acid in all chromatograms. It is interesting that this fatty acid, rarely found in significant amounts in most oils, is abundant in the oil obtained from the berries of sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*), a plant native to Central Asia and Afghanistan. However further analysis should be performed to confirm the presence of this oil in the samples.

Most of the chromatograms from samples of Tepe Narenj (except TN1b) also highlighted propionic acid. This acid has antifungal properties and can be naturally obtained by the degradation of sugars through microbial fermentation (González-García et al. 2017). Finally, analyses performed on TN2b and TN2c using the extraction method of Correa-Ascencio & Evershed (2014) indicate the presence of Pinaceae resin in both samples (also detected by FTIR analyses in the case of TN2b and TN6). According to Agama literature, *Pinus longifolia* resin is employed to prepare the glue (*asthabanda*) and clays (Varma 1970). Terpenoid-based resins have traditionally been used not only as adhesives but also for their waterproofing properties in earthen structures (Eires et al. 2015). Moreover, it is reported that in Bamiyan, Afghanistan “a bituminous substance that was found used on clay plasters, turned out to be an organic resinous matter presumably obtained from the pine (*Pinus longifolia*) wood available locally” (Beas 1991: 28). It also seems interesting to note that the Agama literature describes adding water from the decoction of various tree barks to clays during preparation. This could explain the presence of *n*-alcohols observed in the acid extraction chromatograms, though this hypothesis requires further investigation, as *n*-alcohols are not so specific.

The information gathered points out that multiple organic binders (polysaccharides, resins and proteins) were employed to obtain the desired modelling clay-based pastes, in line with the recipes detailed in Agama literature, but also from what is deduced by traditional knowledge and the data obtained by related research on Gandharan painting techniques (Lliveras-Tenorio et al. 2017; Lliveras-Tenorio et al. 2022; Taniguchi et al. 2022).

Further analyses are needed to verify the presence of milk derivatives in clays, such as ghee or yoghurt. Inspired by the work of the West Bengal clay artists (who nowadays only add gum-based binder preparations to primers and polychromes) and the idea that the Agama recipes were merely ritual and symbolic, until now, it was thought that lipids or proteins should be linked exclusively to painting techniques. But after this first attempt to search for organic compounds in the modelling pastes of Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut samples, all the data suggest that the artists who made Gandharan monumental *terracruda* sculptures were clay alchemists who used multiple substances of different origins (proteins, resins, lipids and polysaccharides) probably in different ways and with different objectives depending on the artefact. These purposes can only be hypothesised for the moment, thanks to studies carried out in earthen architecture, where the use of organic binders is known to be intended to protect against water and enhance durability (Eires *et al.* 2015). Thus, it does not seem unreasonable that the multiplicity of substances mentioned in the Agama literature related to modelling the sacred had a technical function rather than a merely symbolic value, and their inclusion was aimed at obtaining sculptures of greater quality, both artistically and in terms of durability. Interestingly, if we look at the details, adding soil "from the hill of white ants" or "from the house of a crab" would also be consistent with the improvement of the properties of the modelling pastes. Some species of termites (often misnamed white ants) and crabs belonging to the genus *Scopimera* and *Dotilla* are characterized as being humivores (soil-feeders) and mixing soil with saliva to build their nests, which are very resistant in the case of termites (Kumari *et al.* 2006). Both species are present in southern India, where the Agama literature detailing the art of modelling divinity in raw earth originated. This coincidence cannot be overlooked when discussing the creation of *terracruda* sculptures, as it speaks of knowledge based on observing nature and empirical practices, much of which is scarcely preserved today, and that was probably intended to enhance the durability of the earthen artefacts.

7. Conclusions

Despite the complexity of the results, the preliminary information obtained from the analysis of the Tepe Narenj and Qol-e-tut samples points to the use of organic compounds of different origin (polysaccharides, resins and proteins) in preparing the various modelling pastes for the sculptures. The comparison of the analytical results with the information provided by Agama literature, the study of tradition and the results of other research carried out on Gandharan pictorial techniques offers some clues as to the substances that may have been used.

All the gathered data seem to indicate the common use of several organic binders in the modelling of monumental *terracruda* sculpture. The organic sources likely varied from region to region and period to period yet were probably similar enough to achieve the necessary properties for preparing the mortars and plasters. Although further investigation is required, the results appear to align with the multiple substances mentioned in sacred literature. The addition of different binding agents could have been a common practice to obtain the desired properties for earthen mortars or finishing plasters. In this regard, evidence of their presence is crucial to understanding

the technical knowledge behind monumental *terracruda* sculpture, a type of sculpture characteristic of the Silk Roads. Furthermore, this information is also important for designing conservation-restoration interventions, ensuring the key criteria of compatibility and sustainability.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Supplementary Information 1. Fragments of relief (TN4) and mural painting (QT1) sampled.

Supplementary Information 2. Samples taken from the walls of Tepe Narenj (TN6) and Qol-e-tut (QT3)

Supplementary Information 3. Chromatograms obtained on samples TN1b, TN2b, TN7a and QT2c, were 1 is methyl ester of myristic acid, 2 methyl ester of palmitic acid, 3 methyl ester of palmitoleic acid, 4 methyl ester of stearic acid, 5 methyl ester of oleic acid, 6 methyl ester of 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-propionic acid and 7 methyl ester of erucic acid

Supplementary Information 4. Partial gas chromatogram of the lipid extract of samples TN2b and TN2c. In the figure: $C_{n:0}$ are the fatty acids with a specific number (n) of carbons, CL is the cholesterol, dots are phthalates, squares are n-alcohols, and IS is the internal standard (C_{36}).

Supplementary Information 5. Table with oligosaccharidic structures identified in the Figure 5A, 5B and 5C and 6A.

Experimental mass [Da]	Dm [ppm]	Possible oligosaccharide [#]
793.301	13.7	Hex ₄ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
815.190 / 815.203*	100.6 / 84.6*	Hex ₄ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]

831.178	81.8	Hex ₄ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
955.330	13.5	Hex ₅ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
977.280 / 977.278*	43.1 / 45.0*	Hex ₅ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
993.270	29.0	Hex ₅ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
1117.386	8.6	Hex ₆ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
1139.359 / 1139.339*	13.9 / 31.6*	Hex ₆ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1158.337	12.6	Hex ₆ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
1279.455	5.1	Hex ₇ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
1301.428 / 1301.428*	0.8 / 0.8*	Hex ₇ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1317.409	3.8	Hex ₇ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
1441.522	14.6	Hex ₈ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
1463.494 / 1463.474*	9.6 / 4.1*	Hex ₈ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1479.477	13.5	Hex ₈ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
1603.586	20.0	Hex ₉ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
1625.553 / 1625.585*	12.3 / 32.0*	Hex ₉ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1641.545	21.3	Hex ₉ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
1765.688	45.9	Hex ₁₀ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
1787.620 / 1787.629*	19.0 / 24.1*	Hex ₁₀ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1803.606	24.3	Hex ₁₀ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]
1927.737	39.9	Hex ₁₁ [3-AQ/M+H ⁺]
1949.689 / 1949.691*	25.6 / 26.7*	Hex ₁₁ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1965.674	30.0	Hex ₁₁ [3-AQ/M+K ⁺]

1209.369	42.1	Pent ₂ Hex ₃ dHex ₂ [3-AQ/M+Na ⁺]
1217.415	0.4	Pent ₂ Hex ₃ dHexHexA [3-AQ/M+H] ⁺
1239.396	0.5	Pent ₂ Hex ₃ dHexHexA [3-AQ/M+Na] ⁺

Oligosaccharides are derivatized with 3-aminoquinoline (3-AQ) and ionized with H⁺, Na⁺ or K⁺.

* : experimental masses measured on TN2c spectrum

Note: broader range from Hex₄ to Hex₁₁ was obtained and is shown on figure 6A